

Case Report

Coexistence of Bronchopulmonary Adenocarcinoma and Tuberculous Lymphadenitis Diagnosed by CT-Guided Biopsy: A Rare Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis and lung cancer remain significant global public health challenges. While the association between latent tuberculosis and lung cancer is well documented, the coexistence of active tuberculosis and lung cancer remains uncommon.

We report a rare case of coexisting tuberculous lymphadenitis and left bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma in a 71-year-old non-smoking woman. This coexistence, which is difficult to distinguish clinically and radiologically, was diagnosed following histopathological analysis of suspicious lesions obtained through CT-guided biopsy. In addition, this combination of pathologies may also be detected through analysis of bronchoalveolar lavage fluid for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, particularly in patients undergoing evaluation or treatment for lung cancer in regions with high or moderate tuberculosis prevalence.

When lymph node tuberculosis coexists with lung cancer, lymph nodes on the same side as the primary tumor must be carefully examined to avoid errors in TNM clinical classification that may affect treatment strategy.

Management of this coexistence requires a combination of anti-tuberculosis therapy and oncological treatment, including surgical resection, chemotherapy, or targeted therapy depending on the stage of the cancer.

Keywords: lung cancer; tuberculous lymphadenitis; CT-guided biopsy; diagnostic challenge; non-small-cell lung cancer

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis and lung cancer pose significant global health challenges. Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, and tuberculosis continues to be one of the leading causes of death from a single infectious agent [1–2].

Although the coexistence of latent tuberculosis and lung cancer is well documented, with a prevalence of approximately 28.3% [3], the concomitant occurrence of active tuberculosis and lung cancer is rare, with reported prevalence rates ranging from 2% to 5% according to recent data in the literature [4–5].

Both diseases share several risk factors, including active and passive smoking. Furthermore, one condition may predispose to the other, either through chronic inflammation induced by tuberculosis or through profound and prolonged immunosuppression caused by cancer, which may lead to reactivation of latent tuberculosis.

Diagnosing this coexistence is particularly challenging due to overlapping clinical and radiological features. Diagnosis relies primarily on histopathological analysis of suspicious lesions obtained through minimally invasive diagnostic procedures, or on the identification of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in bronchoalveolar secretions via fiberoptic bronchoscopy, particularly in patients living in endemic areas [5].

The management of this dual pathology is complex and requires a multidisciplinary approach combining anti-tuberculosis treatment with surgery and/or chemotherapy, or targeted therapy depending on the stage of the cancer [6].

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We report a rare case of coexisting tuberculous lymphadenitis and left-sided bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma in a 71-year-old non-smoking woman residing in a country with moderate tuberculosis prevalence.

CASE REPORT

A 71-year-old non-smoking woman with a history of hypertension, treated with amlodipine/perindopril, and a prior ischemic stroke, for which she was receiving acetylsalicylic acid, was admitted to the Pulmonology Department on November 24, 2024. She presented with exertional dyspnea and dysphonia in the context of general clinical deterioration and unquantified weight loss that had begun on October 25, 2024. Physical examination revealed functional limitations consistent with sequelae of the previous cerebrovascular event. Serological tests for hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and HIV were negative.

A cervico-thoracic computed tomography (CT) scan performed on November 28, 2024, identified a suspicious apical nodule in the left upper lobe and an abnormal lesion on the anterior aspect of the right vocal cord suggestive of right vocal cord paralysis. This finding was confirmed by bronchoscopy, which demonstrated right vocal cord immobility.

A PET/CT scan using ¹⁸F-FDG performed on December 10, 2024 revealed a hypermetabolic left apical pulmonary nodule (SUVmax: 9.7; size: 12.5 × 15 mm), along with multiple hypermetabolic lymph nodes in the mediastinum and the deep left supraclavicular region. Additionally, a hypermetabolic focus was observed in the right hemilarynx (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. FDG PET/CT images: (A) Whole-body maximum intensity projection (MIP); (B–D) axial fused PET/CT images.

(A) Whole-body maximum intensity projection (MIP).

(B) The black arrow indicates a hypermetabolic focus in the right hemilarynx.

(C) The red arrow indicates a nodule in the upper lobe of the left lung, and the blue arrow indicates a deep left supraclavicular lymphadenopathy.

(D) The orange arrow indicates a mediastinal lymphadenopathy in the aortopulmonary window.

On January 4, 2025, a CT-guided biopsy of the left supraclavicular lymph node demonstrated granulomatous lymphadenitis with caseous necrosis consistent with tuberculous lymphadenitis (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Histological image of tuberculous lymphadenitis

Lymph node parenchyma containing epithelioid and giant cell granulomas, represented by the blue arrow with caseous necrosis represented by the red arrow (HE stain, scale 1/100, magnification x 100).

HE: hematoxylin and eosin.

The patient was initiated on standard anti-tuberculosis therapy using the ERIPk4 regimen (ethambutol, rifampicin, isoniazid, and pyrazinamide; four tablets daily). On January 31, 2025, a second CT-guided biopsy was performed on the left apical pulmonary nodule, followed by histological and immunohistochemical analyses. The results confirmed a diagnosis of pulmonary adenocarcinoma with lepidic growth pattern, showing positive immunoreactivity for TTF-1 and p53 antibodies (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Histological and immunohistochemistry images of lung adenocarcinoma.

(A). Tumor proliferation within the lung parenchyma, showing lepidic growth patterns by the blue arrow and acinar by the red arrow. Tumor cells show moderate cytonuclear atypia (HE stain, scale 1/100, magnification $\times 100$).

(B). TTF-1 immunohistochemical staining reveals strong nuclear positivity in tumor cells, shown by the blue arrow (IHC, scale 1/100, magnification $\times 100$).

(C). Immunohistochemistry for p53 shows nuclear positivity in tumor cells, indicated by the red arrow (IHC, scale 1/100, magnification $\times 100$).

IHC: Immunohistochemical

HE: hematoxylin and eosin.

The coexistence of these pathologies raised two main diagnostic hypotheses: (1) a localized bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma (cT1bN0M0) with associated tuberculous lymphadenitis, or (2) a locally advanced bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma (cT1bN2M0) with associated tuberculous lymphadenitis.

Following the diagnosis of non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC), the patient underwent a comprehensive staging workup. Cerebral magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and bone scintigraphy showed no evidence of metastasis.

During a multidisciplinary consultation meeting (MCM), it was decided to perform a mediastinal biopsy targeting stations 5 and 6 (aortopulmonary window) via uniportal video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS). Intraoperative frozen section analysis was recommended to inform further therapeutic decisions, given the coexistence of malignancy and tuberculous lymphadenitis.

The patient's operability assessment was favorable: spirometry revealed a forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) of 87%, and both transthoracic echocardiography and standard laboratory tests were within normal limits.

Intraoperatively, thoracoscopic exploration using an optical camera revealed a highly adherent lymph node at the aortopulmonary window. The biopsy was performed, but the lymph node was damaged by the incorrectly adjusted electric scalpel, and the extemporaneous examination revealed only a fibrous fragment with nonspecific histological features.

A segmentectomy was performed, along with removal of the celluloganglionic fat and the lymphadenopathy initially biopsied from the aortopulmonary window. A posterior-apical chest drain was placed at the end of the procedure, and all surgical specimens were submitted for pathological examination.

The chest drain was removed on postoperative day 3. The patient had an uneventful recovery and was discharged on postoperative day 5. A follow-up visit was scheduled for 15 days after discharge.

At follow-up, the surgical wound showed satisfactory healing with no signs of complications. Histopathological analysis confirmed an invasive bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma with lepidic and acinar architecture measuring 1.8 cm in length, with a healthy surgical margin located 0.1 cm from the tumor and absence of tumor cells in the celluloganglionic fat and adenopathy of the aortopulmonary window. The patient was classified as pT2N0M0.

Regarding the lesion in the right vocal cord, an examination carried out by an ENT specialist concluded that there was chronic inflammation and the patient was put on anti-inflammatory medication

DISCUSSION

Lung cancer accounts for approximately 1.8 million deaths worldwide, representing about 18.7% of all cancer-related mortality [1]. Tuberculosis caused an estimated 10.8 million new cases and 1.25 million deaths globally in 2023 [2].

The coexistence of lung cancer and active tuberculosis is rare, with reported prevalence rates ranging from 2% to 4.7% [4-5] and is more frequently observed in countries with high or moderate tuberculosis incidence [5].

Morocco is considered a country with moderate tuberculosis incidence, **with 35,000 reported cases in 2021, corresponding to** an incidence rate of 94 per 100,000 population, according to the World Health Organization (WHO) [7]. Although no data on the prevalence of coexisting

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lung cancer and active tuberculosis in Morocco were found in the literature, the country's tuberculosis epidemiological context may explain the concurrent occurrence of active tuberculosis and lung cancer in our case.

Likewise, the coexistence of these two diseases is favored by a common factor, namely active or passive smoking. This is proven by the study of Morales-Garcia et al [5], in which all 15 patients with concurrent pulmonary tuberculosis and lung cancer were either current or former smokers. This finding does not apply to our patient.

However, her advanced age (71 years), comorbidities (hypertension and history of ischemic stroke), and residence in a country with a moderate tuberculosis incidence, may explain the development of tuberculous lymphadenitis.

Nevertheless, it is also possible that tuberculous lymphadenitis was the initial pathology, potentially contributing to carcinogenesis in the left apical pulmonary nodule. Because inflammation associated with active tuberculosis has been implicated in oncogenic processes, several studies suggest a potential link between tuberculosis-related inflammation and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) mutation [8].

The simultaneous diagnosis of active tuberculosis and lung cancer can be particularly challenging due to the overlapping clinical and radiological signs, making it difficult to distinguish between isolated tuberculosis, lung cancer, or their coexistence [6]. In our case, the diagnosis was established after histopathological analysis of suspicious PET/CT lesions (pulmonary nodule and left supraclavicular lymphadenopathy) obtained via CT-guided biopsy. This diagnostic approach aligns with the existing literature, where confirmation of both conditions generally relies on biopsy analysis performed from infectious sites, malignant tumors, or regional lymph nodes [9]. In contrast, Morales-Garcia et al. [5] reported a diagnosis established during tuberculosis screening in lung cancer patients living in high-endemic areas, using acid-fast bacilli (AFB) smears and mycobacterial culture from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid obtained by bronchoscopic examination.

In our case, the histological subtype of lung cancer was adenocarcinoma, which is consistent with several studies identifying adenocarcinoma as the most frequently observed subtype in cases of coexisting tuberculosis and lung cancer worldwide [10]. In contrast, in the Middle East, squamous cell carcinoma is the most frequently associated with tuberculosis [5].

The most common form of active tuberculosis observed in association with lung cancer is pulmonary tuberculosis [5]. In our case, however, the patient presented with tuberculous lymphadenitis, which complicated TNM clinical classification of the left upper lobe bronchopulmonary adenocarcinoma.

It proved difficult to determine whether the aortopulmonary window lymphadenopathy was due to tuberculous disease or metastatic spread. Therefore, the multidisciplinary cancer board recommended a biopsy of the mediastinal lymphadenopathy (aortopulmonary window) to establish an accurate staging (TNM), essential for appropriate therapeutic management.

Unfortunately, the frozen section examination was inconclusive due to poor biopsy sample quality, likely due to thermal damage caused by the electrocautery. According to a literature

review, most cases of lung cancer diagnosed simultaneously with active tuberculosis are identified at advanced stages (stage 3 or stage 4) in approximately 60% of patients [5]. However, the histopathological analysis of the surgical specimen allowed us to respond to our concerns by classifying the tumor as pT2N0M0.

Management in our case began with antituberculous treatment, followed three weeks later by segmentectomy of the left apical pulmonary nodule with clear surgical margins. Our attitude corroborates the literature which recommends initiating anti-tuberculosis treatment three weeks before surgical resection of resectable lung cancers coexisting with tuberculosis [6].

CONCLUSION

The coexistence of bronchopulmonary cancer and active tuberculosis is rare, generally occurring in regions where the incidence of tuberculosis is moderate to high. Diagnostic difficulty arises from their overlapping clinical and radiological features.

Histopathological analysis of biopsy samples and microbiological testing of bronchoalveolar secretions remain essential for accurate diagnosis.

In countries like Morocco, systematic consideration of tuberculosis in patients with lung cancer, especially in the presence of suspicious lesions, may improve diagnostic precision and therapeutic outcomes.

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DECLARATIONS

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